

Pest resistance—other pests

Resistance of deepwater rice (DWR) varieties to ufra disease in Assam

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We field-tested 100 DWR varieties and breeding lines to determine their resistance to ufra disease, caused by *Ditylenchus angustus*, during 1989 and

1990 wet seasons (Apr/May–Oct/Nov).

We sowed seeds in 10-m rows at 20 × 20-cm spacing in an ufra-infected area. Susceptible checks Rangabao and NC492 were planted in rows alternately with test entries. Local agronomic practices were followed. Susceptibility was expressed as the percentage of infected tillers/hill (see table).

Rangabao and NC492 averaged 90% infected tillers/hill, which led to total crop collapse. □

Reaction of DWR varieties to ufra disease in Assam, India, 1989-90 wet seasons.

Entries	Ufra incidence (% infected tillers/hill)	Reaction class
Rayada 16-06	0	Resistant
Rayada 16-05	11–25	Moderately resistant
Rayada 16-07		
Rayada 16-08		
Rayada 16-09		
Bazail 65		
Neghri, Laldhepa, Panikekua, Herepi, Duatkalam, Maguri	26–50	Susceptible
Padmapani (red), Padmapani (white)		Escaped disease because of early crop maturity (Sep)
Adalibao, Amona, ARC/152, ARC5778, Badam, Badel, Bagadhhepa, Bakul, Bordhan, Buralibao, Bogphul, Beta, Borjahingia, Bogajul, Biroi, Bormaguri, Chengabao, CR670-37, CR671-19, Dalbao, Dolmaguri, Digabao, Dhepabao, Dubaribao, Dubraj, FRG7, Gajepsali, Hatisali, Harkana, Hida, HBA 1, Indunayan, Ikarasali, IET10003, IET10005, IET10006, IET10008, IET10021, IET10027, IET11181, IET10048, IR48193-20-3, IR42580-13-2, IR47393-306, IR47619-20-3, IR11141-6-1-4, Julbao, Katibao, Kajalibao, Kekua, Kehjol, Kalamani, Laodubi, Khamtisali, Latamaguri, LPR85, LPR372, LPR56-97-115, LPR56-203-18, LPR56-304-38, LPR96-10, LPR254-164, LPR302-94-68, LPR425-42-116, LPR550-387-24, Mahsuri, Monoharsali, Moimonsingia, Neghri, NC492, ND4R21, Panimaguri, Patki, PJNB96-10, PJNB95-2, PJNB94-18-1, PN56-205-43-12, Rangabao, Rengunsali, Rupahi, Sonamukhi, Solpona, Sorsori, Tarabao, Tulasibao	50	Highly susceptible

Stress tolerance

Low light tolerance of rice hybrids and their pollen parents

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The productivity of F₁ rice hybrids under low-light conditions during monsoon season has not been well analyzed.

We studied tolerance for low light in eight hybrids derived from CMS sources V20 A, IR54752 A, and Intan Mutant A (IMA), their pollen parents (restored) and checks (Ratna and Swarnaprabha) during 1990 wet season. Plants were spaced at 15 × 10 cm in 1.2 m² field plots and fertilized with 60 kg N/ha.

Plants were shaded with wood screens from 40 d after planting to harvest to simulate low light (50% normal) conditions. Controls were maintained under normal sunlight (about 320 cal/cm² per d). The experiment was replicated three times and laid out in a split-plot design. Light treatments were in main plots, and hybrids and pollen parents in subplots. Growth duration of hybrids varied from 117 to 145 d (see table).

Photosynthetic rate (Pn) was measured with the Li-6000 Portable Photosynthesis system under optimal light of about 900 μE/m² per s. Crop photosynthesis was the product of Pn and leaf area index (LAI). Both Pn and Pn × LAI were generally higher in IR54752 A hybrids, especially in IR54752 A/Vajram. It also had the highest dry matter, yield, and harvest index under both normal light and low light. Such efficiency may be attributed to higher physiological and yield potential of the restorer. Yield per day of hybrids and parent were also highest in both light regimes.

IR54752 A/Vajram showed significant standard heterosis in yield under low light compared with the best low light-tolerant check Swarnaprabha. Yield heterosis over its restorer, though negligible under normal light, was considerable under low light (10%).

Photosynthetic efficiency and effect of low light (50% normal) from 40 d after planting to harvest on dry matter and yield of rice hybrids, pollen parents, and standard varieties. Cuttack, India.

Hybrids and parents	Total duration (d)	At flowering		Total dry matter at harvest (g/m ²)		Yield (g/m ²)		Harvest index	
		Pn (mg CO ₂ /dm ² per h)	Pn x LAI (g CO ₂ /m ² per h)	Full light	Low light	Full light	Low light	Full light	Low light
<i>Hybrid</i>									
V20 A/Milyang 46	123	27.2	8.3	693	362	318	62	45	17
V20 A/IR36	117	31.1	8.4	634	346	209	102	33	29
IR54752A/IR54	137	34.1	13.4	1201	483	413	159	34	33
IR54752A/IR46	137	28.4	10.8	1115	497	343	83	31	17
IR54752A/Vajram	145	36.1	14.3	1276	670	537	285	42	42
IR54752A/Swarna	142	32.1	13.5	1041	393	345	73	33	18
IMA/ARC11353	126	31.5	10.6	960	583	127	37	13	6
IMA/IR27315	126	34.1	10.8	947	468	169	110	18	23
<i>Pollen parents (restorers)</i>									
Milyang 46	123	29.6	5.5	520	229	241	42	46	18
IR36	120	23.4	7.3	888	344	400	65	45	19
IR54	140	30.6	14.0	826	507	391	181	47	36
IR46	140	25.4	9.6	1221	410	307	60	25	15
Vajram	145	31.4	12.4	1262	606	527	258	42	42
Swarna	145	31.5	13.9	968	512	463	124	47	24
ARC11353	140	26.4	10.3	1246	588	551	221	44	37
IR27315	126	31.6	10.0	851	472	333	151	39	32
<i>Checks</i>									
Ratna	123	34.2	9.0	859	204	325	64	38	31
Swarnaprabha	120	31.4	10.7	1146	619	537	231	47	37
Mean	132	30.6	10.7	980	460	355	128	37	24
LSD (0.05)	Variety	2.1	1.2	23	25	—	—	—	—
	Treatment	—	—	54	41	—	—	—	—
	V at same T	—	—	32	36	—	—	—	—
	T at same V	—	—	48	36	—	—	—	—

Stress tolerance—adverse soils

Performance of selected rice genotypes on acid sulfate soils in the Kiralakele area of southern Sri Lanka

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Plant height, survival percentage, and Fe toxicity scores for selected tolerant lines in normal and toxic soils.^a Kiralakele area, southern Sri Lanka, 1989.

Variety	Normal soil		Toxic soil		Toxicity score ^b at	
	Plant height (cm)	Survival (%)	Plant height (cm)	Survival (%)	4 WT	8 WT
C37	77.3	100	73.6	93.3	1	1
Bw 295-5	83.2	100	74.4	93.3	1	1
Bw 85	121.0	100	108.0	86.6	2	3
At 69-2	71.6	100	62.4	80.0	2	3
At 69-5	89.6	100	77.3	80.0	2	3
At 76-1	88.5	100	80.7	66.6	2	3
IET249	85.6	100	73.5	66.6	3	3
Bg 350 (control)	73.7	100	—	0	7	9

^aMeans of 2 seasons. ^bBy the Standard evaluation system for rice scale. WT = weeks after transplanting.

IR54752 A/Vajram was developed at Maruteru, Andhra Pradesh, India, in the coastal monsoon belt. It has potential for low-light monsoon areas of eastern India where medium- to long-duration varieties are preferred for post-monsoon harvest. This hybrid, however, cannot be produced commercially because of its unstable female parent IR54752 A. □

119 ppm active Fe, and 45-55 ppm available Al.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications during two cropping seasons in 1989. Three-wk-old seedlings were transplanted at three seedlings/hill, 20- × 20-cm spacing, in 3-m single rows.

Plants were fertilized at planting with NPK (18 kg N/ha, 24 kg P/ha, 45.6 kg K/ha). Plants were also topdressed with 62 kg N and 26.6 kg K/ha 6 wk after transplanting (WT).

Another set of the same genotypes was transplanted in a nearly normal soil with pH 4.8-5.3, 5-6% organic C, 12-15 ppm available P, 80-84 ppm active Fe, and 8.7-9.3 ppm available Al. Bg 350, which is susceptible to Fe toxicity, served as control in both seasons.

We recorded visual symptoms of Fe toxicity (bronzing of leaves and stunted growth) 4-8 WT. Plant height and survival percentage at maturity were recorded (see table).

Under toxic conditions, plants of the susceptible check and some other selected lines (Bw 351, Bw 78, Bw 272-8, Bw 297-2, Bw 288-2, Bg 379-2, Bg 1565, Bg 1564, Bg 300, V-15) died at an early growth stage. C37 and Bw 295-5 were least affected. Bw and At varieties and IET249 also showed few Fe toxicity symptoms.

A package of agronomic practices is being tested to obtain the best yields from Bw and At in affected soils. These varieties are widely used in hybridization programs for improving tolerance level and yield. □